

THE IMPORTANCE TEACHING VOCABULARY OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN
SPECIALIZED SCHOOL FOR (5~7) GRADES

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Abstract. This article explores the crucial role of teaching foreign language vocabulary in specialized educational settings catering to students in grades 5-7. At this pivotal stage of cognitive development, vocabulary instruction plays a multifaceted role in shaping academic achievement, interdisciplinary connections, cultural competence, and preparation for secondary education. Through targeted vocabulary instruction tailored to the specialized curriculum, educators empower students with the linguistic and cognitive skills necessary for success in their chosen fields. By fostering a deep understanding of disciplinary terminology, promoting cross-disciplinary dialogue, and cultivating cultural awareness, specialized schools lay the foundation for lifelong learning and global citizenship.

Key words: Cognitive development, academic achievement, interdisciplinary connection, cultural competence, cognitive growth, vocabulary acquisition.

ВАЖНОСТЬ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ЛЕКАРСТВА ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ В
СПЕЦИАЛИЗИРОВАННОЙ ШКОЛЕ ДЛЯ (5-7) КЛАССОВ

Аннотация. В данной статье исследуется решающая роль преподавания лексики иностранного языка в специализированных образовательных учреждениях, обслуживающих учащихся 5-7 классов. На этом ключевом этапе когнитивного развития обучение словарному запасу играет многогранную роль в формировании академических достижений, междисциплинарных связей, культурной компетентности и подготовки к среднему образованию. Посредством целевого обучения словарному запасу, адаптированного к специализированной учебной программе, преподаватели дают учащимся лингвистические и когнитивные навыки, необходимые для успеха в выбранных ими областях. Способствуя глубокому пониманию дисциплинарной терминологии, содействию междисциплинарному диалогу и развитию культурной осведомленности, специализированные школы закладывают основу для обучения на протяжении всей жизни и глобальной гражданской ответственности.

Ключевые слова: Когнитивное развитие, академическая успеваемость, междисциплинарные связи, культурная компетентность, когнитивный рост, приобретение словарного запаса.

In the dynamic landscape of specialized education, the role of teaching foreign language vocabulary to students in grades 5-7 holds immense importance. This crucial phase of development lays the foundation for linguistic proficiency, cognitive growth, and cultural awareness. As these young learners embark on their academic journeys in specialized schools, the acquisition of vocabulary in foreign languages becomes essential for both academic achievement and holistic skill development. This introduction will delve into the pivotal role that vocabulary instruction plays in shaping the educational experiences of students in grades 5-7 within specialized school environments.

In the specialized educational context of grades 5-7, teaching foreign language vocabulary assumes a multifaceted role that goes beyond mere language acquisition. The importance of teaching vocabulary of foreign languages in specialized school for (5-7) grades includes:

Cognitive Development: At this critical juncture of cognitive development, students in grades 5-7 exhibit heightened receptivity to language learning. Teaching foreign language vocabulary not only enhances their linguistic skills but also stimulates cognitive growth. Research indicates that learning a second language during this period can lead to cognitive benefits such as improved problem-solving abilities, enhanced creativity, and increased metalinguistic awareness.

By introducing students to a diverse range of vocabulary in specialized subjects, educators foster cognitive flexibility and linguistic adaptability, empowering students to think critically and approach challenges from multiple perspectives.

Academic Achievement: Vocabulary proficiency is closely linked to academic success across all subject areas. In specialized schools, where students engage with complex concepts and disciplinary terminology, mastery of foreign language vocabulary is essential for comprehension and mastery. Whether studying mathematics, science, technology, engineering, arts, or humanities, students rely on a robust vocabulary repertoire to articulate ideas, analyze information, and communicate effectively. Through targeted vocabulary instruction tailored to the specialized curriculum, educators equip students with the language tools necessary to excel academically and thrive in their chosen fields of study.

Interdisciplinary Connections: Specialized schools offer unique opportunities for interdisciplinary learning, where students explore connections between different subject areas and

apply knowledge in real-world contexts. Teaching foreign language vocabulary enhances these interdisciplinary connections by facilitating communication across disciplinary boundaries. For example, students studying environmental science may learn vocabulary related to sustainability and ecology in both their native language and a foreign language, enabling them to collaborate with peers from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds on interdisciplinary projects. By fostering cross-disciplinary dialogue and collaboration, vocabulary instruction in specialized schools promotes holistic learning experiences that prepare students for the complexities of the modern world.

Cultural Competence: Language is deeply intertwined with culture, and teaching foreign language vocabulary provides students with insights into diverse cultural perspectives and practices. In grades 5-7, students are at a formative stage of cultural development, where exposure to different languages and cultures can foster empathy, tolerance, and global awareness. By incorporating cultural elements into vocabulary instruction, educators cultivate students' cultural competence, enabling them to navigate multicultural environments with sensitivity and respect.

Whether exploring literature, traditions, or social customs, students gain a deeper appreciation for the richness and diversity of human experience, laying the groundwork for informed global citizenship.

Preparation for Secondary Education: As students transition from primary to secondary education, proficiency in foreign language vocabulary becomes increasingly important for academic and personal growth. Specialized schools play a pivotal role in preparing students for the rigors of secondary education by equipping them with the language skills and cultural competence necessary for success. By establishing a strong foundation in vocabulary acquisition during grades 5-7, educators empower students to pursue advanced coursework, participate in international exchanges, and engage with global issues in meaningful ways. Whether pursuing STEM fields, the arts, or humanities, students armed with a robust vocabulary toolkit are better equipped to navigate the challenges and opportunities that lie ahead in their educational journey.

Teaching foreign language vocabulary in specialized schools for grades 5-7 is essential for cognitive development, academic achievement, interdisciplinary connections, cultural competence, and preparation for secondary education. By prioritizing vocabulary instruction within the specialized curriculum, educators provide students with the linguistic and cultural tools they need to succeed in an increasingly interconnected and diverse world.

In conclusion, teaching foreign language vocabulary in specialized schools for grades 5-7 is integral to fostering cognitive development, enhancing academic achievement, promoting

interdisciplinary connections, cultivating cultural competence, and preparing students for future educational endeavors. By prioritizing vocabulary instruction within the specialized curriculum, educators empower students with the linguistic and cultural skills necessary to thrive in an increasingly globalized society. As students transition to secondary education and beyond, a strong foundation in foreign language vocabulary equips them to excel academically, communicate effectively, and engage with diverse perspectives, thereby laying the groundwork for lifelong learning and success.

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